

What will be the effect on socio-economic mobility of the UK government's plan to impose value-added tax on school fees?

The British Government, as part of the 2024 budget, announced a policy to impose a 20% value-added tax (VAT) on all private schools in England and Wales, reversing the centuries of tax exemptions that these schools have enjoyed under the definition of “public benefit” outlined in the Charities Act of 1601.¹ This question can be simplified into two sub-parts: first, what impact will this policy have on the private education system? And to what extent does increasing spending on education contribute towards reducing income inequality?

This essay, in addressing these two sub-questions, will use the impacts of the plan, both positive and negative, on wealth distribution, educational outcomes resulting from greater government spending, scholarships offered by private schools and external factors like socio-economic conditions of students and economic growth to conclude that the proposed VAT is likely to have a positive impact on socio-economic mobility in the UK.

This question on the educational divide is of particular significance in the UK’s case, where educational outcomes differ widely between private and state schools as a result of private schools spending nearly three times as many resources per pupil as state schools.² This paves these students a gateway to future success at university and increases these students' chances of entering the British elite, defined on economic, reputational, and positional grounds, by 94 times, creating a substantial divide in the quality of employment.³

Figure 1: Domination by Private School Alumni of the British Elite⁴

Private schools, being fee-charging institutions with a history of higher odds of admission into the British elite as represented in Figure 1, have perpetuated the socio-economic divide generation after generation by availing their benefits to only families with sufficient ability to pay. The average fees for a private day school in 2018 were £14,280 for day schools and £33,684 for boarding schools, representing a 75% increase in real terms from 2000;⁵ however, the Gini coefficient of Britain during the same period did not show any major changes.⁶ This has manifested in the concentration of private school participation in the top income decile.⁷

In this case, the VAT on private education could be considered progressive taxation. Increased taxation will raise school fees, primarily for high-income families, which the government anticipates will raise £1.725 billion per year by 2029-30.⁸ The revenue generated is expected to be used to improve the state's education system, which is currently severely underfunded and understaffed. The percentage of local authority schools running a budget deficit has steadily increased to 15.3%. Thus, increased funding could help ensure that state schools have adequate resources, potentially resulting in a Robin Hood effect in the long term.⁹

A Robin Hood effect occurs when income is redistributed from the wealthy to the less fortunate.¹⁰ This effect can be empirically represented on a Lorenz curve, which is a graphical measure of income inequality, that represents the share of cumulative income as a function of the percentage of households. Typically, a VAT tax is regressive, but in this context it can have a positive impact on income inequality, leading to a reduced Gini coefficient and leftward shift of the Lorenz curve as seen in Figure 2. This effect is reinforced by existing literature, which has found a strong positive correlation between income inequality and education inequality, which creates a strong case for improving the quality of education for upward socio-economic mobility.¹¹

Figure 2: Shift of Lorenz Curve¹²

The government's policy proposal to fund state schools using VAT collected on private schools helps in reducing inequality in the short run and ensuring greater mobility through education. However, there is a risk of misallocation of resources, which can fundamentally deter education outcomes from increased spending.

Comparing average scores on the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) test with education spending reveals a negligible impact of increasing education spending on test scores for high-income countries.¹³ This indicates that improvements in education quality are more likely to be caused by improvements in observable factors affecting the quality of education. While increased school financing can positively impact factors like decreased student-to-teacher ratio and class sizes, it is not always necessary.¹⁴

For instance, higher cantonal spending on education from 2004 in Switzerland, a comparable high-income country, has yielded no major results in increasing either educational mobility or quality.¹⁵ Another deterrent to the UK's ability to improve its state of public schools can be explained by Baumol's Cost Disease.¹⁶ Increasing productivity in a few sectors of developed economies puts pressure on other sectors to increase wages correspondently without any

increase in productivity. A similar argument could be made with teachers, wherein they are overpaid and the education industry still faces great competition to keep them in the face of higher wage prospects in other industries.¹⁷ In the UK's case, this theory points to fundamental issues in teacher retention and recruitment that can't be solved with greater educational spending.

Further, critics of the policy argue that a sudden increase in the number of students in state schools could also exacerbate the pressure on state schools.¹⁸ An increase in the costs of private schools in Britain could lead to a decrease in the number of parents being able to afford private schools. The aforementioned systemic factors, along with this exodus to the state school system, could greatly hamper the quality of education received by students. That being said, the British government only expects a 10% increase in tuition costs and a more manageable increase of 35,000 students in the public education system over a long period of time.¹⁹ Combining the government's analysis with the positively skewed income distribution of families participating in the private education system points to the demand for private education in the UK being largely price inelastic. This determination makes the "exodus to public schools" unlikely.

A more substantial cause for concern with regards to the quality of education received by pupils is the likely decline in the number of scholarships and bursaries offered by private schools. UK private schools give approximately £483 million in scholarships and bursaries, which offer an opportunity for students from low-income households to access the opportunities available at these schools.²⁰ An increase in costs for private schools, caused by a part of the VAT being absorbed by private schools, will reduce the scholarships and bursaries provided by the schools to ensure that their total costs are not significantly impacted.

The impact of these scholarships on the larger populace is countered by Malcom et al., who assert that these scholarships are primarily means-tested and that only 3.2% of the student population received a scholarship for over 75% of the school fees.²¹ This is indicative of the fact that these bursaries are targeted at a limited select group of students and that for the average household, with an annual income of £37,430, the fee is not affordable even with a bursary.²² Seeing that such scholarships have a limited effect in creating an economically diverse student body in private schools, their utility in socio-economic mobility can be deemed to be limited. Furthermore, the benefits offered by scholarships to students with special abilities are likely to be provided by local authorities under the Education Health and Care Plan (EHCP) for students with Special Needs and Disabilities (SEND), which is eligible for tax refunds.²³

Another fundamental argument about the effect of increased spending on education is its impact on the students themselves. High school test scores act as proxies for human capital and future income and can be used to determine the direct impact of increased education spending on increasing income.²⁴ In addition to the quality of teaching provided, external factors like financial situation, social factors, inherent mental aptitude, connections of high-income families, etc. impact a student's academic performance, which cannot be overcome by increased spending on education.²⁵ The impact of these externalities can be said to outweigh that of government spending, as confirmed by a greater impact of increased spending on the academic performance of lower grades as opposed to that of higher grades.²⁶ This also plays into Michel Sandel's criticism of meritocracy, which promotes the idea that true meritocracy is a myth and that in any supposedly fair process like admission into elite colleges, external factors around a pupil's socio-economic situation are a bigger determinant of their future success.²⁷ A similar type of public spending campaign in France to promote school choice for

all income groups, did not lead to satisfactory results as the multi-tiered education system continued, perpetuating differences in performance.²⁸

It is also important to acknowledge the importance of external economic factors in reducing economic inequality. In the UK's case, real GDP growth is expected to be between 1 and 2%, which is less than that of many emerging economies, even though it is one of the highest in the G7.²⁹ It is an established fact that economic growth is correlated with decreasing unemployment and potentially an increase in the number of high-income jobs.³⁰ Given the fairly low growth forecasts resulting primarily from lower productivity, job creation may not occur at a fast enough pace, negating the effects of increased education spending.³¹ In such a situation, inheritance might outpace income creation, continuing the cycle of income inequality.

Figure 3: UK Economic Growth Forecast³²

Having examined various ways in which increased spending on education may not yield expected results, it is important to highlight examples where higher spending has resulted in improved education outcomes. Studies in the United States show that increased spending raises graduation rates and reduces the likelihood of adult poverty by 3%.³³ In another case, a \$1,000 increase in education expenditure was found to increase test scores by 0.0316 standard deviations.³⁴ The UK, being a developed economy, has high-quality institutions with low levels of corruption and strong local governments; thus, it has a higher chance of implementing policies brought about by greater education spending more successfully.³⁵ This factor may, to a certain degree, counter the negative effects of the low economic growth and socio-economic background of students. That being said, resource allocation is a major determinant of the outcome of increased education spending.

The most straightforward use for education sending would be to increase the number of academic resources available, such as individual tutoring or more qualified teachers.³⁶ While these are important, navigating the more nuanced aspects, such as the speed of these policy changes and the adverse outcomes of teacher dissatisfaction due to the increased number of classes, will help achieve the larger goal of equality in the quality of education received by pupils.³⁷ From a policy perspective, adding the socioeconomic situation of students attending a particular private school to the National Funding Formula (NFF) used for spending allocations might help offset the disadvantages to students because of their particular situation.

With regard to the impact of the VAT tax on reducing income inequality by increasing the quality of education provided to low-income households, the effect is likely to be disproportionate for different income groups. While there is likely to be a broad positive impact, subject to how resources are allocated, schools with a concentration of poor-income

families are likely to be more impacted than those with middle-income household concentration.³⁸ The reason for this is twofold: firstly, schools with middle-income households are likely to get less funding and therefore are more likely to misuse the resources.³⁹ An argument of diminishing returns may also hold in this case, with schools that are highly underfunded having greater potential to improve up to a certain level than a school that is only slightly underfunded. This demonstrates the potential of the VAT tax to uplift the quality of education received by the most marginalized schools in the country.

The recurrent issue of resource misallocation that comes along with spending tax revenue on the public education system can be hedged against by policy interventions, which will further help in reducing income inequality. Affirmative action programs at Russell Group universities, which act as gatekeepers to the British elite, may help reduce the income divide.⁴⁰ Additionally, the nationalization of a few public schools across a large geographical area may promote competition among public schools, leading to higher quality education.

In conclusion, the VAT tax implemented by the UK government is likely to deliver on the promised upward social mobility guarantees by proportionately taxing high-income households and using revenue generated to advantage low-income households. Increased educational spending is also likely to improve both the quality of education and educational mobility, thus fostering a skilled workforce. The evidence presented in this essay points to the likelihood of broader economic gains from this policy outweighing any disruptions or inefficiencies due to resource misallocation; thus, making this taxation policy an important step towards creating a more equal and meritocratic education system while also reducing stratifications in British society.

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